

Reactions of (i) Aluminium Tertiary Butoxide with Acetyl Bromide and (ii) Aluminium Tribromide with Tertiary Butyl Acetate

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The reactions of aluminium tertiary butoxide and acetyl bromide have been studied. The addition of one mole of acetyl bromide to aluminium tertiary butoxide forms monobromide ditertiary butoxide, which, with another mole of acetyl bromide, appears to give the dibromide monotertiary butoxide derivatives. Further, these products appear to react with tertiary butyl acetate formed in the reaction itself, giving acetate derivatives. The above is confirmed by a detailed study of the reaction between aluminium bromide and tertiary butyl acetate, which have been found to result in the acetate derivatives. A plausible mechanism of the reaction has been suggested.

Considerable work has been done on the reactions of acetyl halides and the aluminium alkoxides^{1,2,3}. With the normal and secondary alkoxides, the reactions proceed in a straightforward manner yielding halide alkoxides; which can be represented in general by the following equation :

(where R = normal or secondary alkyl group and n=1, 2, or 3)

However, the tertiary butoxide showed a different behaviour towards acetyl bromide and the reaction was found to be incomplete as shown by the Br : Al ratio in the product. The exceptional behaviour of tertiary butoxide was attributed to steric hindrance caused by ramified alkyl group in a general way.

In a recent⁴ study of the reaction of silicon tetrachloride with tertiary butyl acetate it has been found that silicon tetraacetate is formed at the room temperature in quantitative yield. Similarly the acetates of aluminium⁵, zirconium⁵, and titanium⁶ have been shown to be formed by the reaction of tertiary butyl acetate on the chlorides of corresponding metals. In view of the observations already made on the reactions of acetyl chloride with the tertiary butoxides of aluminium³, zirconium⁵ and titanium⁶, it was considered worthwhile to investigate the reactions of aluminium tertiary butoxide with acetyl bromide.

1. Mehrotra and Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1962, **39**, 23.
2. Mehrotra and Mehrotra, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1962, (4) **16**, 251.
3. Mehrotra and Misra, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 717.
4. Mehrotra and Pant, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1963, **5**, 321.
5. Mehrotra and Misra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 43.
6. Mehrotra and Misra, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 500.

A perusal of the data in Table I clearly indicate that the reaction of acetyl bromide and aluminium tertiary butoxide is straightforward yielding the monobromide ditertiary butoxide derivative in the equimolecular proportions; with the second mole of acetyl bromide the dibromide derivative appears to be formed by the equation :

However, the dibromide monotertiary butoxide derivative appears to react with tertiary butyl acetate produced in the reaction itself, with the replacement of bromide group by acetoxy group as represented by equation (iv) :

In the rest of molar ratios of the reactants, the reaction appears to follow a similar pattern (equation iv) leading to the formation of acetoxy products. In these reactions with aluminium tertiary butoxide, acetyl bromide appears to be more reactive than the chloride, an observation based on the Halide : Aluminium ratio in the products².

The correctness of the latter side reaction has been confirmed by carrying out a detailed study of the reactions of aluminium tribromide with tertiary butyl acetate. The results in Table II show that the reaction is exothermic and facile up to the formation of the monobromide diacetate product;

Later on the reaction becomes slow and the triacetate of aluminium is obtained under refluxing condition with an excess of tertiary butyl acetate ;

The most plausible mechanism of this reaction may be represented as :

EXPERIMENTAL

All glass apparatus fitted with interchangeable standard joints was employed and adequate precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Fractionations were carried out in column packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total condensation variable take-off still head.

Aluminium tertiary butoxide was prepared with aluminium turnings and anhydrous tertiary butyl alcohol⁷; it was sublimed (160°/1.00mm) and analysed before use. Found : Al, 10.9. Calc. for Al(OBu^t)₃ : Al, 10.97%.

Acetyl bromide was carefully fractionated and the fraction distilling at 76°C being collected.

Aluminium tribromide was prepared by the action of bromine with aluminium turnings using the method of Winter and Cramer⁸. It was distilled twice at 120°C/10 mm to a colourless crystalline solid and analysed.

The preparation, purification and drying of other reagents and solvents were carried out as described earlier³.

Analytical Method : Aluminium and bromine were estimated as oxinate and silver bromide separately. Acetoxy group was estimated by titrating a weighed sample with N/10 sodium hydroxide using phenolphthalein as indicator. Initially it was tested that aluminium tribromide as well as triacetate require about 3.0 equivalent of sodium hydroxide. In the absence of any acetoxy and bromide group (as in the case of aluminium tertiary butoxide) the aqueous hydrolysis of the product would not produce any acid, and hence the solution becomes alkaline to phenolphthalein with the first drop of alkali. On the basis of these observations the number of acid (acetoxy + bromide) groups attached per aluminium atom in a particular derivative has been estimated by alkalimetric titrations, as the tertiary butoxide group would not interfere in these titrations; the bromide groups per gram atom of aluminium have been separately determined.

TABLE I
Reactions of aluminium tertiary butoxide with acetyl bromide

Reaction Mixture	Molar ratio	Conditions of the experiment	Nature of the product	ANALYSIS							
				Found				Required			
				%Al	%Br	Br/Al	Alk. eq. in moles	%Al	%Br	Alk. eq. in moles	
Al(OBu ^t) ₃ (2.98g), CH ₃ COBr (1.49g) in benzene 16.0g.	1:1	Refluxed 100°C/2 hrs.	White crystalline solid turns yellowish brown (3.07g). AlBr(OBu ^t) ₂	11.0	31.4	0.97	1.0	10.66	31.6	1.0	
Al(OBu ^t) ₃ (2.71g), CH ₃ COBr (2.71g) in benzene 15.8g.	1:2	Kept 36 hrs. at room temperature (35°C).	White solid (2.69g) AlBr 0.85 (OAc) 1.35 OBu ^t	11.62	22.9	0.65	2.0	11.64	22.4	2.0	
Al(OBu ^t) ₃ (3.99g), CH ₃ COBr (6.98g), in benzene 20.0g.	1:3	Refluxed 100°/2 hrs.	White solid (3.47g) AlBr 0.95 (OAc) 0.95 (OBu ^t) 0.5	12.5	9.1	0.25	2.5	12.47	9.2	2.5	
Al(OBu ^t) ₃ (2.59g), CH ₃ COBr (3.21g).	1:4	Kept at room temperature (35°C/24 hrs.) Refluxed 100°C/2 hrs.	White solid AlBr 0.1 (OAc) 0.8	12.9	7.7	0.2	2.94	12.9	7.5	3.0	

7. Wayne and Adkins, "Organic Synthesis", 1941, Vol. 21, p. 8, John., Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York.
8. Winter and Cramer, *Ind. and Eng. Chem.*, 1940, (6), 32, 856.

Reactions of aluminium tertiary butoxide with acetyl bromide (Table I): Since preliminary trials showed that the reaction between acetyl bromide and aluminium tertiary butoxide is exothermic so these reactions were carried out at lower temperature to avoid any early side reactions. Acetyl bromide (in required ratio) was admitted in a clear solution of aluminium tertiary butoxide in benzene at 0-5°C. After being shaken well, it was either allowed to stand overnight at room temperature (35°C) or gently refluxed. The solid products were obtained by distilling the volatile fractions from the reaction mixture under reduced pressure.

TABLE II

Reactions of aluminium tribromide with tertiary butyl acetate

Reaction Mixture	Molar ratio	Conditions of the experiment	Nature of the product	ANALYSIS						
				Found				Required		
				%Al	%Br	Br/Al	Alk. Eq. in moles	%Al	%Br	Alk. Eq. in moles
Al Br ₃ (2.55g), Bu ^t OAc (1.11g) in benzene 18.5g.	1:1	Room temp. (35°C)/1 hr.	Viscous brown solid (2.47 g) Al Br ₃ (OAc)	10.4	58.4	1.92	3.0	10.9	65.05	3.0
Al Br ₃ (4.08g), Bu ^t OAc (3.56g), in benzene 21.5g	1:2	Room temp. (35°C)/1 hr.	White solid (light brown) (3.71 g) AlBr _{1.4} (OAc) _{1.6}	11.1	47.3	1.4	2.96	11.4	47.9	3.0
Al Br ₃ (2.16g), Bu ^t OAc (1.88g), in benzene 19.0g.	1:2	Refluxed 100°C/1 hr.	White solid (1.79g) Al Br (OAc) ₂	11.9	35.3	1.0	2.97	11.98	35.5	3.0
Al Br ₃ (2.29g), Bu ^t OAc (3.01g) in benzene 16.4g.	1:3	Refluxed 100°C/1 hr.	White solid (1.94g) Al Br _{0.7} (OAc) _{1.3}	12.2	25.3	0.7	3.0	12.3	25.5	3.0
Al Br ₃ (4.85g), Bu ^t OAc (30.05g) excess in benzene 8.5g.	1: large excess	Refluxed 100°C/2 hrs.	White solid (3.77g) Al (OAc) ₃	13.2	—	—	3.0 OAc, 86.7%	13.2	—	3.0 OAc 86.7%

Reaction of aluminium tribromide and tertiary butyl acetate (Table II): The solution of aluminium tribromide in benzene was caused to react with tertiary butyl acetate in required ratio. All the reactions were highly exothermic and were carried out in a cold bath (0-5°C). After the reaction mixture had been shaken it was either allowed to stand at room temperature (35°C) or refluxed. The volatile fractions were removed and the products were dried under reduced pressure at room temperature (35°C). The final products were white amorphous solids except in the 1:1 molar ratio, where it was a viscous brown solid.

For the preparation of aluminium triacetate the aluminium tribromide in benzene solution was added dropwise to the well cooled tertiary butyl acetate with stirring. A.

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white insoluble product separated out of the reaction mixture. It was gently refluxed for 2 hr., the excess of solvent was decanted off and the product was dried under reduced pressure at 40°/1.5 mm.

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